

NEW MYXOMYCETE RECORDS FROM NATURE RESERVES OF UKRAINE

Leontyev D.V.¹, Eliasson U.², Kochergina A.V.³, Morozova I.I.⁴

¹National Pharmaceutical University, Kharkov, Ukraine; ²Göteborg University, Sweden;

³Volgograd State Medical University, Russia; ⁴V.N. Karasin National University, Ukraine

The biodiversity of Myxomycetes in Ukraine has been intensively investigated during the last few years. Special attention has been paid to nature reserve territories as islands of native biodiversity in such an urbanized country as Ukraine. During 2006-2008 summer-autumn seasons we collected myxomycete material under field conditions (fc) and as moist chamber cultures (mc) in 'Baydary Valley' Regional Reserve (BVRR), situated in South-West Crimea, 'Medobory' Nature Reserve (MNR) in the West Forest-Steppe Region, and 'Gomolsha Forests' National Nature Park (GFNNP) in the East Forest-Steppe Region of Ukraine. Some of our earlier collections (2002-2004) from the Kharkov Region of Ukraine were also re-examined. Some species found appeared to be new (*) or rare for Ukraine. Here we briefly present some noteworthy records.

***Comatricha elegans* (Racib.) G. Lister** – GFNNP, fc, single colony of sporangia on dead wood of *Populus tremula* L., VII.2006. Found in Ukraine only once, in Crimea Peninsula, by K.O. Romanenko (2006).

***Comatricha ellae* Härk.** – GFNNP, fc, single specimen on dead wood of *Pinus sylvestris* L., VII.2006. Found in Ukraine twice, both times in Crimea Peninsula, by T.I. Kryvomaz (1998) and K.O. Romanenko (2006).

***Diderma floriforme* (Bull.) Pers.** – GFNNP, fc, several colonies of sporangia on bark of fallen trunk of *Quercus robur* L., VII.2006. Found in Ukraine once, in Right-Bank Polyssia Region (Zelle, 1925).

****Didymium applanatum* Nann.-Bremek.** – GFNNP, fc, single specimen on living moss *Myurella* sp., VII.2006.

****Didymium bahiense* Gottsb.** – GFNNP, mc, single specimen on leaf litter of *Quercus robur* L., VII.2003; Kharkov Region, mc, abundant, on germs of *Hordeum vulgare* L., X.2004; Kharkov Region, mc, several specimens on bark of *Armeniaca vulgaris* Lam., V.2004.

***Didymium dubium* Rostaf.** – BVRP, mc, scattered fructifications on dead branch of *Juniperus oxycedrus* L., V.2007. Found in Ukraine only in GFNNP by D.V. Leontyev (2006).

****Didymium flexuosum* Yamash.** – GFNNP, mc, single plamodiocarp on leaf litter of *Quercus robur* L., VII.2005.

****Didymium pertusum* Berk.** – MNR, mc, single sporangium on leaf litter of *Quercus robur* L., IV.2007.

****Didymium verrucosporum* A.L.Welden** – BVRP, mc, single sporangium on dead branch of *Juniperus oxycedrum* L., bark of *Quercus pubescens* Willd, X.2007.

****Fuligo rufa* Pers.** – GFNNP, fc, abundant on fallen trunks and stumps of *Pinus sylvestris* L., VI-VII.2006. This species has not previously been formally reported for Ukraine, but may have been incorporated in and identified as *F. septica* (L.) F.H.Wigg.

****Licea pusilla* Schrad.** – BVRP, mc, group of sporangia on dead branch of *Juniperus oxycedrum* L., X.2007.

***Lindbladia tubulina* Fr.** – GFNNP, fc, abundant on fallen trunks and stumps of *Pinus sylvestris* L., VI-VII.2004, VI-VII.2005. This species was recorded for Ukraine long ago by J.Krupa (1889) and H.Krzemieniewska (1934) in the Carpathians.

****Paradiacheopsis acanthodes* (Alexop.) Nann.-Bremek.** – GFNNP, mc, single specimen on bark of *Quercus robur* L., VII.2003; BVRP, mc, dead branch of *Juniperus oxycedrum* L., X.2007.

****Perichaena quadrata* T.Macbr.** – BVRP, mc, abundant on bark of *Fagus orientalis* Lipsky, VIII.2006.

****Stemonaria gracilis* Nann.-Bremek. et Y.Yamam.** – BVRP, mc, two specimens on dead branch of *Fagus orientalis* Lipsky, VIII.2006.